

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing

Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Dualisation of Rhythmic Patterns

Cheuk Lun Isaac Lee

Supervisor: Sergi Jordà

Co-supervisor: Behzad Haki

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Abstract

This thesis examines the concept of dualisation of rhythmic patterns, the representation of a rhythm using only two voices. From different literatures and discussions with professional musicians, it is suspected that from the perspective of a musician, this concept holds a certain degree of meaningfulness, replicable to produce similar dualisations, and the concept is universally applicable to different drummers. The aim of this dissertation is to verify these claims from musicians empirically. In order to obtain data for analysis, dualisation of rhythmic patterns are collected from experienced percussionists. A total of 19 hours of data were collected, and by analysing them a correlation between dualisations and the perception of the concept can be drawn. Several properties of dualisation can be confirmed, such as the meaningfulness and the replicability of dualisation from the same drummer; however, some original claims remain disputable, noticeably the universality of dualisation.

Keywords: rhythm, rhythm analysis, dualisation, dataset;

1. Introduction

Music is a temporal art; an experience arranged from front to back that can only be perceived with its representation in time [1]. As Isidoro de Sevilla wrote, “sounds are held by the memory of men; they perish, because they cannot be written down” [2], this temporal fundamental characteristic causes problems when people want to retain the art and not let it vanish when time passes. In contrast with other art forms such as visual art, because of this temporal property it was impossible to record it “as it is” until the industrial revolution where sound recording devices were invented [3]. Therefore, rather than trying to document music exactly as it is, many traditions tried to represent music in a symbolic representation, such as notes and chords.

Such symbolic representations are more comparable to a depiction of common knowledge than a genuine representation in an audio signal processing domain [4]. The human understanding, cultural background, and the fundamental perception of music contribute to these symbolic representations [5], and the essence of music in the compositional processes is exposed via symbolic representations as opposed to just the sound itself [4]. From the old-school sheet music to the modern MIDI files, new symbolic representations are often invented according to our understanding of music and the advancement of technology. They might appear to be vastly different, but inherently both sheet music and MIDI are trying to portray a temporal experience symbolically.

Dualisation of rhythmic patterns is one of these symbolic representations; the aim is to transform a multi-voice rhythmic pattern by another 2-voice representation while maintaining the core essence of the original pattern. Percussion symbolic representations arose along the melodic notation relatives, beginning with only describing at which moment should the note be played [6]. With the development of Western music, rhythm began to play a much more important role, however, developing from a monophonic snare drum tradition [7] and stemming from a melodic notation system [6], rhythmic patterns on drum sets do not have a representation developed on its own, and specifically designed to express rhythm rather than a system that stems from the melodic realm. Some attempts are made in order to tackle this insufficiency by find the root essence of rhythm: fundamental properties of rhythm were explored and

represented in multi voices, this will be further explored in the next session; practical approaches such as tap2drum in GrooVAE by Magenta [8] and project from Rue [9] are growing in recent years, however these approaches remain to symbolise rhythm in a monophonic way.

If a monophonic representation of rhythmic patterns could successfully represent a multi-voice rhythm, that is proof that rhythm can be further reduced to a closer form to its essence. The next question would be the dimension of the reduction; that is what will be the effect when different scopes of dimension are applied. Would a 2-voiced (or more) symbolic representation of rhythm meaningful, and does it relate more or less to our perception of the essence of rhythm? This is a simple question yet lacking a straightforward answer.

1.1 Motivation

This is not the first time that anyone suggested the concept of dualisation. Kotowski did his Master thesis in the Universitat Pompeu Fabra on this exact topic [10]. Using a 2-voiced representation to capture the essence of rhythmic patterns is an experimental exploration of new symbolic representations. However, voice reduction is still a relatively new concept and it is difficult to obtain sufficient data for both monophonic [9] and diaphonic representations [10]. Without data as ground truth, Kotowski resorted to compressing rhythmic information into a lower dimensional form and tried to retain the essence by this method; notwithstanding the theoretical justifications, this previous project ultimately ended with a very insightful note, yet inconclusive results.

This does not mean that the concept of dualisation has crumbled; it still remains a strongly intuitive and understandable concept, both for myself, my supervisors, and numerous percussionists that I have been discussing with. I am thus motivated to reinvestigate into this concept using another approach.

1.2 Objective

The objective of this project is to verify the meaningfulness of this concept, and the correlation between dualisation and our perception of the essence of rhythm. Upon consideration of the lack of sufficient data and the previous attempt, a qualitative approach is favoured: discussing and collecting data from professional percussionists,

and answer the questions surrounding the concept of dualisation by analysing the data collected and the insights from percussionists.

2. State of the Art

Albeit the idea of rhythmic pattern dualisation is yet to be explored thoroughly in the computational field, there are plenty of suggestions and implications of this concept from different disciplines. These justifications of dualisation will be reviewed below in the fields of traditional rhythmic analysis and psychological rhythmic perceptions, as well as the tools being frequently implemented computationally.

2.1 Rhythmic analysis

2.1.1 Traditional Rhythmic Hierarchy and Layer Formation

Akzenttheorie

Traditionally, rhythm refers to the serial pattern of variable note durations in a melody [11], where it consists of different relative timings in between note onsets. Metre, on the other hand, refers to the organisation of rhythm perceived into regular repetition of stressed and unstressed beats. This distinction is fundamental for the understanding of rhythmic perception [12], and thus how the hierarchies and layers are formed automatically when a rhythmic pattern is heard.

Akzenttheorie, accent theory in German, is an understanding of metre developed first by Sulzer and Shelling in the 18th century [13], and expanded upon by Koch [14]. Time in a Newtonian sense is a “homogeneous, even flowing” canvas where it “serves as a receptacle for events” [15]. Streams of event instants in a rhythm can then be divided and organised into a metrical hierarchy via the characteristics of metrical accent; the listener will group the notes together following the rules provided by the metre, generating a front and back layer of the rhythm that humans perceive as different.

Figure 1: A rhythm (first row) is painted on a time canvas (second and third row), where metre divides and organises the rhythm into hierarchical structures. Image taken from [15], p.14.

Figure 2: Metrical accent interpreted as a durationless instant on the time canvas, where A and B, α and β refers to the accented and unaccented perception of beats according to the layers formed. Image taken from [15], p.19.

Although *Akzenttheorie* focuses on the analysis of accents in relation to rhythm and metre, it is clear that with the Newtonian understanding of time implied, layers and hierarchies will be formed automatically; or in other words if the human sense of time is flowing and continuous, with a degree of repetition of rhythms the human mind will create vertical hierarchies to group the notes together as patterns.

Geometry of Rhythms

The modern interpretation of rhythm has been expanded from a one-dimensional tunnel view, just as its harmonic counterpart. Toussaint reinterpreted rhythm by using a geometrical representation, incorporating the rhythmic hierarchies and layers into an analysis on rhythms from different cultures with an Euclidean algorithm [16]. A “necklace” representation of rhythm is applied to represent a constantly repeating rhythm, and a Euclidean algorithm is used to represent a group of similar rhythms. From a combinatorial viewpoint, there are many more possible combinations of notes on the necklace, yet only a few of the Euclidean representations would be popular enough to be standardised not only in the west, but also music around the world.

Figure 3: “Necklace” representation of 2 Cuban origin rhythms. (a) is the tresillo and (b) is the cinquillo. Image taken from [16].

With this necklace representation, more attributes of rhythm are analysed, such as rhythmic depth, syncopatedness, complexity etc. Later in his book [17], qualities that contribute to the goodness of a rhythm are examined. One of these attributes is “inversional combinatoriality”, which refers to that if the rhythm and its complement are both played simultaneously, and their acoustic properties such as timbre or intensity differ, the listener has the impression that the rhythm is switching roles; it is first introduced as a compositional rule by Arnold Schoenberg [18], and it is investigated in the rhythmic domain. Toussaint states that by playing a rhythm with both hands, it emerges from the process of accenting the proper onsets with each hand while maintaining all the durations between left- and right-handed strokes equal to one pulse. In his own words, “the downward motions of the hands trace all the pulses of the rhythm”.

Toussaint would propose a different representation of rhythm in the latter chapters, namely the Alternating-hands Box Notation. Two side-by-side sequences of boxes are placed next to each other, and the two columns represent the two hands. The differences between the two rhythms are highlighted by the onsets and the motion of both hands in this manner of playing may be conveniently described with a notation which indicates all the pulses present in the rhythmic cycle. It is also stressed that notes from both hands can be reversely played in order to have a clearer understanding of the rhythm, indicating that rhythm on left and right hand has no differences.

Figure 4: The Alternating Hand Box Notation from the book [17], Ch.32 p.244.

Although the work of Toussaint serves more like a representational convenience of rhythm, it does provide a source of intuitiveness of dualisation.

E-T system

Jaki Liebezeit, a German drummer famous for his contributions to the rock and electronic music sphere, proposed a dualising model named the E-T system [19]. He claims that rhythms can be represented by two symbols only: the dot and the dash. It can be realised that such rhythms are played on two drums, with the two hands from the drummer. While this system is only his personal comprehension of rhythm, it generalises rhythmic patterns specifically played on the drum set. Combining it with the theory of rhythm geometries, it serves as a rationale behind the concept of rhythmic dualisation.

2.1.2 Music Tradition Approaches to Rhythm

As the theory of rhythm geometries also analyses rhythms all around the world, it would be interesting to look at how other cultures handle rhythm to examine if this concept of dualisation can be applied universally.

Bell Pattern and Claves

A bell pattern is a two-voiced pattern frequently used in West African music, it is usually used as a key pattern to suggest a temporal organisation for different instruments and musicians [20]. This pattern is used from the Sub-Saharan [20], to West Africa to the central lands of Congo and the Nyusa lands in Southeast Africa [21]. Agawu [22] claims that the notoriously complex rhythm in West African music can be represented with a bell pattern, which usually could also be played with two-voiced percussion instruments.

This African tradition migrated to the new world during the colonial period. Rooted in the Caribbeans, the Clave cross-rhythm splits the beat into two voices, one regular beat and another irregular [23]. It is hence evident that this two part representation of rhythm was also independently developed outside of the European sphere of influence.

Development of the Drum Set

The representation of dualisation can also be seen in the development of drum sets. The modern drum set is an American invention [24] [7]. Similar to the cultural norm in the U.S. during the enlightenment, it is a melting pot of percussions all around the world: using the European drumming traditions at its core, and incorporating different instruments from other cultures such as the Chinese influenced tom-toms [25] [7] and the Afro-Cuban clave [26].

The instinctive dualisation perception of drummers can be demonstrated by its development, as different techniques were established from the European drumming core. First seen in the Swiss Confederacy in the medieval period [27], drum rudiments were being discussed for military usages; various combinations of two hands strokes on a snare drum were explored to aid with coordinations within a mercenary army. Later influencing the French army [28], and ultimately different rudiment practices in different European countries [29]. This snare drum military tradition was carried along to the new world, sometimes spreading the two-hand combinations into using both feet [7], such as playing the kick and the bass drums. From the late nineteenth century trap kit to the modern drum kit, this 2-handed snare drum tradition still remains a strong influence to the musicians even when playing styles like latin, especially those who were trained with a Western drumming tradition.

2.2 Human Perception of Rhythmic Patterns

2.2.1 Rhythmic Memory in a Human Brain

Essence in Rhythm

As described above, there is a consensus that the human brain would group different events in the rhythm together and perceive it in a particular way. According to Parncutt [30], the event percepts can often be grouped with different ways, hence producing different hierarchies. Some of the underlying principles of grouping notes are event perceptual attributes such as loudness and pitch [31], timbre [32], or onset time and duration [30]; it could also be previously experienced and familiar patterns, for example one can quickly recognise and identify a familiar melody or song just by the rhythm tapped alone if the melody or song has a distinct rhythmic structure. One study [33] showed that if a song has rhythm as its underlying compositional feature, participants would be able to recognise the song just by the tapping of the rhythm alone, even if they were not given a list of possible songs. Another similar study [34] showed that three songs in particular yielded uniformly high identification rates: Jingle Bells, Wedding March, and Deck the Halls. As demonstrated, rhythm can induce cue validity when it is specifically designed as an underlying compositional feature, and it could be recalled just by giving the essence of the rhythm. In an environment of solo percussion instruments, such as a drum set, there would only be percussive events happening, either it is the perceptual attributes, or the underlying essence.

Rhythm Learning and Tapping

On the other hand, neurophysiologists have shown that while musicians tap along a rhythm, they are actively retrieving, selecting, and maintaining the musical beat [35]. Musicians were required to tap along various beats with different complexity while an fMRI machine would be used to observe their brain activity; each beat were played for three times with a silence period in between repetitions, the musicians would be able to learn and familiarise themselves to the beat for the first time, while they would tap along the beat in the next two repetition. The activities recorded are divided into two parts, learning the beat and tapping along.

Figure 5: (A) shows the experimental procedure, where the beat is repeated for three times. The musicians will familiarise themselves in “Find Beat”, and tap along in “Tap Beat”. (B) presents the data of different aspects. Image taken from [35]

Results show that beat finding and beat tapping excites largely overlapping regions in the brain. The superior temporal gyrus (STG), premotor cortex, and ventrolateral PFC (VLPFC) regions in the brain will be activated when the musician is actively learning and tapping along the rhythm. The regions of VLPFCs are highly related to music perception, comprehension, and performance, suggesting that they were actively involved in finding the essence in the beat, and try to present it out as an abstract representation of single voice tapping. Contrastingly, the BG activities, the region in the brain contributing to detection of temporal regularity and motor responses, were similar throughout the experiment, showing that the musicians were not just following the beat in the temporal sense purely; they were interacting with the music actively and certain transformations were occurring in their brain.

Figure 6: Results of the experiments. (A), (B), and (C) presents the brain activity regions recorded in the fMRI during different stages of the experiments. The bar charts below show the intensity of the activities. Image taken from [35].

2.2.2 Pulse Perception and Dualisation

Pulse is defined as a simple sequence of equally-spaced event percepts [30], it may be regarded as the basis of rhythm perception because it distinguishes between rhythm and non-rhythm, where if given a rhythmic pattern the human brain will actively search for an underlying pulse. Furthermore it has been found true across all musical cultures [30].

A common belief of this automatic pulse perception is related to certain periodicities of the human body such as heartbeats and footsteps [36]. Synchronisation of movement to the pulse also exists, whether it is in the form of hand movements [37], walking [38] [39], or even movement between people [40] such as dancing.

The neural activities of this particular kind of synchronisation is well researched in neurophysiology. One study [41] showed that when given a temporally regular stimulation, EEG neural activities of the participants would entrain to such a regular

pulse, and automatically synchronise with the frequency of the stimulation. Participants were given a 2.4Hz rhythm in either a binary or ternary metre, and they were required to deduce the underlying beat and group the rhythm according to their understanding of metre while their EEG responses were being recorded by an MRI device. Results have shown that there were different layers of neural oscillation, these oscillations would agree with the metre being played. It suggests that the internal representation, and thus the comprehension of the essence of rhythm, divides between metre and beat, and forms different layers in the brain.

Figure 7: The averaged result of the pulse perception experiment. Here shows the EEG activities in the participants' brain when presented with a steady beat in either a binary or ternary metre. Image taken from [41].

2.3 Rhythm Computing

2.3.1 Tools for Rhythm Computing

In order to handle music in a computational environment, musical content must be represented in a way that is configurable algorithmically. The choice of the representation and the encoding of musical information is highly associated with the architecture structure and its input and output [4]. Therefore it is important to examine the tools of musical content treatment in a computational sense.

MIDI

While the contents could be represented in an audio representation, the usage of raw sound signals is inherently very different from symbolic representations, that concerns various concepts like notes, durations and chords, as it requires some processing and transformation of the raw materials. In his book [4], Jean-Pierre explained the some reasons to apply a symbolic representation rather than raw audio signals, such as: the majority of the current deep learning systems are symbolic, the essence of music (and thus also in rhythm) is occurring as a natural consequence of active composing, which could be exposed by symbolic representation either notated by humans or subjected to analysis.

Musical Instrument Digital Interface, frequently abbreviated as MIDI, is a technical standard that contains information about a protocol, a digital interface and connectors for interoperability between various controllers [42]. It carries musical events in messages that specifies real time performance data such as notes, note onsets and velocities. Since it contains the necessary symbolic representations of an entire drum set, MIDI is widely used to represent rhythmic related information.

Groove MIDI dataset and Works by Magenta

In 2019, the Groove MIDI dataset [8] was released by the Magenta team under Google AI. It was released as a training dataset alongside a bigger project, namely GrooVAE, that consists of a class of models for generating and controlling expressive drum performances [8]. Ten musicians were recruited for the creation of this dataset, and their performances were recorded on a Roland TD-11 electronic drum kit with a metronome set at a specific tempo by the musician. The performers excel in different

genres of music, and different styles were being recorded. The performance data was then annotated according to a primary and secondary style, tempo, beat or fill, time signature, and other symbolic representations of the track. The entire dataset contains about 13,6 hours, 1.150 MIDI files, and over 22.000 measures of drumming; all the tracks are available in NoteSequence, MIDI, and audio format, and they are segmented into two or four bar chunks. This enormous dataset was introduced to train GrooVAE models originally, but it is certainly a well-compiled rhythm dataset on drum sets.

It is also worth mentioning that the Magenta team has created another symbolic representation of musical events named NoteSequence or `note_seq` as a Python module [43]. It is specifically designed to assist the exploration of machine learning in the process of creating art and music. It is advantageous in converting tracks to representations useful for model training such as Tensors, also easily translating between different other representations such as MusicXML and MIDI. The above-mentioned Groove MIDI dataset is also available in this representation.

2.3.2 Computational Models for Rhythm

Amongst the Music Generation field, several interpretations have been experimented and models were implemented. From rule based generations according to rules of counterpoint, to the Markov chains related models, there are numerous predecessors before nowadays. While they certainly stand as an important evolutionary milestone in the field, the usage of neural networks has been rising in popularity in recent years.

Computational models for rhythm itself are however way less explored, let alone dualisation. There are a few analyses on rhythm, mainly adding a perceptual interpretation into the computationally representations. Both analyses and rhythm generations will be described below.

Metrical Weight Profile

While formulating the Generative Theory of Tonal Music, Lerdahl and Jackendoff [44] proposed a structure in order to consider the rhythmic hierarchy from a psychological viewpoint. This structure is a metrical weight profile of a 16-pulsation rhythm experienced by a listener; it describes the importance of different pulses, where the more important ones will be more accented, and vice versa.

Palmer and Krumhansl [45] proposed another weight profile based on psychological principles. Experiments have shown that the above mentioned structure does exist, but the accent weightings for musicians and non-musicians are quite different.

Figure 8: The above mentioned metrical weight profiles. On the left is the profile by Lerdahl and Jackendoff[44]. On the right are the experimental results from Palmer and Krumhansl[45]. The strength of the metrical accent corresponds to different time units in a 16-pulsation rhythm with different weights. Image taken from [46].

Metrics of Rhythm Similarity

In order to develop compositional tools for drum rhythms, Gómez Marín compiled a set of rhythmic descriptors that is useful in a polyphonic environment for a drum set in his doctoral thesis *Similarity and Style in Electronic Dance Music Drum Rhythms* [46]. The entire drum set is divided into three frequency ranges: low, middle and high; these ranges are divided according to the individual sounds of instruments among the drum set. Descriptors are then designed to be able to handle the three ranges alone, as well as the entire polyphony. The descriptors are: density which describes the number of onsets, analysing both three ranges and the entire polyphony; syncopation-ness which describes the syncopation value using a Hamming distance [47] [48], analysing both 3 ranges and the entire polyphony; number of instruments of the entire polyphony; and the complexity, a quotient of the syncopation value and the sum of onset of each frequency range.

Frequency range	syncopations		densities			number of instruments	complexity
high	hisync	polysync	hiD	hiness	StepD	NOI	hisyness
mid	midsync		midD	midness			midsyness
low	losync		loD	lowness			losyness

Table 1: List of different rhythmic descriptors and their target frequency range analyses. [46]

There are also other agnostic mathematical metrics being applied onto rhythmic similarity. The cosine distance is a straightforward comparison between two vectors; similarity can be measured by calculating the cosine angle between the two vectors, and the distance would be the complement of similarity.

$$d_c(X, Y) = 1 - \text{Similarity}_c(X, Y) = 1 - \frac{X \cdot Y}{\|X\| \|Y\|}$$

Equation 1: Cosine distance of two vectors X and Y .

Hamming distance and the Levenshtein distance are also two major metrics in string matching. The Hamming distance of two strings is the number of differences between two strings with identical length, and the Levenshtein is a fuzzy matching that is also applicable on strings with different length. While the Hamming distance only calculates the existence of mismatches, it does not calculate how far the mismatches are. The Levenshtein distance also considers insertions, deletions, and transpositions, rather than solely the replacement to form the other string. Both distances are first used as a rhythm distance measurement by Toussaint[49] through comparing the onsets of two rhythms, and later works showed that it can also be applied onto syncopation [47] and onto velocity [46].

$$d_{Ham/Lev}(X, Y) = \sum |x_i - y_i|$$

Equation 2: Hamming and Levenshtein distance. x_i and y_i are the elements with the same index of the 2 different strings X and Y . Both of them compare the difference between two strings, but

Hamming just considers replacement, while Levenshtein also includes insertions, deletions, and transpositions.

The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient is often used in the analysis of rhythm; it computes the correlation of two lists of numbers with their rank variables. After every element of the two lists are assigned a rank variable according to their value, the two lists are compared to see how well their relationship can be described using a monotonic function, a strictly increasing or strictly decreasing function; therefore this coefficient can indicate whether the two lists are in complete positive or negative correlation, or any value in between. Experiments have shown that the Spearman's rank correlation can be used to analyse rhythmic complexity [50], and it is also applied to other rhythmic descriptors in [46].

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6\sum d_i^2}{n^3 - n}$$

Equation 3: The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. r_s is the coefficient, where d_i is the difference between two rankings and n is the number of datapoints.

The aim of the dualisation of rhythmic patterns is to represent polyphonic rhythms from a drum set as a 2-voiced representation, that is there should not be a discrimination between left and right; in other words, if the two channels are flipped, the representation should be equally valid. Hence, by applying the Jaccard Index [51] the difference can be eliminated. By taking the ratio of intersection over union from the two sets, the situation can be simplified into a comparison of two lists without treating left and right differently.

$$J(X, Y) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A| + |B| - |A \cap B|}$$

Equation 4: Jaccard Index of 2 sets.

Further elaborations about the specifics of applying these metrics to dualisation will be discussed in Chapter 4 Evaluation.

Kotowski's Method

The previous method to this dualisation problem done by Kotowski [10] proposed two machine learning algorithms that were built upon the GrooVAE [8] network topology for rhythm humanisation, which is a combination of two architectures using LSTM cells: the Variational Autoencoder and Sequence to Sequence Learning.

The Variational Autoencoder, abbreviated as VAE, belongs to a bigger architectural family of autoencoders. Autoencoders are designed to approximate an identity transformation by reducing the dimensional representation of data, which means that the compression of data would not only reduce complexity but also retain the essence of the information. This architecture consists of three parts: the encoder, bottleneck, and the decoder. The encoder and the decoder were built with the non-linear neural network cells, LSTM cells in [10] as well as the GrooVAE model. Encoder compresses information into a lower dimension that can pass through the limitation set by the bottleneck layer, while the decoder does the opposite to expand the compressed information back into the original, ideally the same as the original. The VAE, introduced by Kingma and Welling [52], adds the probabilistic model into both the encoder and decoder, which increases the performance of an Autoencoder with a Gaussian distribution.

Figure 9: Architecture of the VAE. The green part is the encoder, red part is the bottleneck layer, and the blue part is the decoder. x and x' are desired to be identical as the entire VAE

models an identity transformation. The probabilistic module is typical of VAE. Image taken from [10].

RNNs are able to transform sequential information into fixed-length vectors. However, in situations such as the implementation of VAEs, it is more valuable to represent sequences with different lengths. Sequence to Sequence Learning, abbreviated as Seq2Seq, suggested by its name it is designed to map variable-length sequences to another variable-length sequence. This architecture has its roots in the field of natural language processing when it was first introduced by Cho et al. [53], revolutionised how data can be represented. The encoder is an RNN network that could handle a variable-length sequence, and transform it into a context vector which is a fixed-length vector. It then proceeds to decode the context vector back to another variable-length sequence using another set of RNN cells.

Figure 10: Architecture of Seq2Seq. A sequence with length of three (ABC) is being converted to a sequence with length of four (WXYZ). The context vector is transferred between cells as a fixed-length vector. Image taken from [10].

The previous work of Kotowski and GrooVAE used an architecture that combines both the VAE and Seq2Seq with LSTM cells. 2 bar rhythms are broken down into a 32 length vector, put into the encoder to compress information, then decode back to achieve dualisation.

Figure 11: Architecture of GrooVAE. One of the architectures used in the work of Kotowski. It is used to obtain the two dualisation results where it was obtained from modifications of this architecture. Image taken from [10].

2.4 Summary of the State of the Art

Dualisation is a huge topic that is related to multiple fields of science, it is never easy to justify such a broad claim: the essence of every drum pattern could be represented by a

two-voiced symbolic representation. Yet from the multiple literatures above some understanding of how much is currently known about can be achieved.

Although literatures in the rhythmic analysis section are not strong scientific evidences, the striking similarity between a lot of cultures is obvious that they have some opinion about describing rhythm with layers and hierarchies. From the *Akzenttheorie* to the geometries of rhythm, the understanding of rhythm from these musicians clearly does not comprehend directly as events arranged in time; there are certain layers formed within the rhythm itself where humans perceive as different parts, hence a grouped and simplified hierarchy from a polyphony. This hierarchy formation is further supported by the human instinct of the usage of two hands, such as the E-T system. When looking into music from different cultures, the backbone of rhythm usually boils down to a 2 voiced representation, and with the development of the drum set from a Western snare drum tradition the 2 voiced representation is also present in the minds of modern musicians.

There are further psychological proofs that rhythm has its essence, and humans perceive rhythm with these essences in our brains in two parts; it can be justified by our walking pattern. On the other hand, when a person is tapping to a rhythm, the rhythm is not only followed in a temporal sense, it is constantly being understood, comprehended, and then performed out. There is also proof that the humans will automatically synchronise with a steady beat, perceiving as a pulse. This perception of an underlying pulse is said to originate from human movements such as dancing or walking, therefore it might be related to our only two hands playing a rhythm, thus dualising the rhythm.

As there are evidences that such dualisation of rhythm exists, as well as tapping to a rhythm would produce an understanding of the rhythm; we would like to know through experiments and the collection of musicians dualising rhythms and with the various rhythmic similarity metrics, would there be any correlation of the data that reflect this instinctive and understandable phenomenon.

3. Methodology

As mentioned in the introduction section, a qualitative approach to the concept of dualisation is favoured: discussing and collecting data from professional percussionists, and answering the questions surrounding the concept of dualisation by analysing the data collected and the insights from percussionists. Therefore the following paragraphs will be explaining the entire process of the experiment, starting from the design, and onto the on-site data collection sessions, and finally some ways that are intended to investigate the data collected.

3.1 Experiment Design

The main idea of this experiment is to document if and how professional percussionists dualise rhythms. The following sections will be first introducing how the original rhythms were prepared, and experiment variations deployed for different analysis.

3.1.1 Data Preparation

In order to document the dualisations of rhythm, the original rhythms have to be prepared. Groove MIDI dataset [8] provides over 22.000 measures of rhythms that were recorded by drummers at Magenta. The data is structured in 503 sessions of recordings, and each session was played with a metronome and labelled with a certain genre. The scope of our experiment would be investigating the dualisation of 2-measure rhythms with a time signature of 4/4, the entire session from Groove MIDI dataset would be excessive; therefore the Groove MIDI dataset had to be first preprocessed and curtailed in order to obtain good loops for the participants to dualise.

2-bar Sample Selection

As every session was played by an individual drummer with a dedicated tempo and style of rhythm, it was decided to select only a single 2-bar sample from each session in the Groove MIDI dataset. The data was first filtered and left only sessions with a time signature of 4/4. In order to select the most representative 2-bar loop from each track, the entire session was first segmented into 2-bar segments, and each segment was compared with all other segments using a cosine distance. The distances of each

segment with other segments were summed and the candidate with the highest similarity was chosen to represent the entire Groove MIDI session.

Figure 12: Cosine distance calculation of each 2-bar segment. The upper figure shows a heat map indicating the cross distance of every segment, and the lower figure shows the most similar candidate and it will be selected to represent the entire Groove MIDI session. This figure only shows one of the 503 tracks being processed.

Verification of the Selected Tracks

As the above process is done automatically, the selection of loops were only based on the cosine distances. Later trial sessions of the experiment discovered that some of the 2-bar loops were not practical, the main reason would be that it just consisted of 2-voices, making the process of dualisation trivial; however 1-voice loops are retained as there might be variations when dualising the single voice. Some tracks also exhibited unusual behaviours that would affect the experiment, such as complete silence tracks.

Therefore, 388 loops were verified manually to remove trivial and unusual loops. This leaves the final dataset with 345 individual 2-bar loops.

Genre Distribution of the Final Selection

Yet, the final selection still has a problem: the genre heavily favours popular music types, most noticeably rock but also funk, latin, and jazz. Since an unbalanced data is not desired, a variation of an experiment used an adjusted selection from these 345 loops. However, the other two data collection sessions remained the same since all the tracks could be dualised. The distribution of the 345 loops are plotted below.

Figure 13: Distribution of the 345 loops used for the data collection sessions.

3.1.2 Variations of the Experiment

Mass Data Collection

The original intention was to simply collect dualisation versions of the 345 loops from different drummers; the scope of sufficient data would be collecting 10 hours of dualisations from 10 different drummers, which every session would consist of 72 loops. The justification of this scope would be that if all sessions were successfully done, it would contain at least 2 variations for each loop that can be compared.

According to this plan, these 345 loops were randomised in order, and distributed among 10 sessions without repetition in a single session. As previous trial participants suggested, the 72 loops in each session were then arranged according to the

syncopation-ness in the rhythm similarity metrics in order to provide a gradually increasing difficulty of loops during the experiment.

Repetition Experiment

However, the available number of participants were greatly overestimated as only 2 participants were involved in the mass data collection mentioned above. One participant offered to take part in 4 hours per day in an entire week of data collection sessions, therefore the mass data collection plan was modified and the effects of repetition were focused.

In this variation, the intention was to investigate how different would the dualisations be from the same drummer on different tracks. For this experiment, 2 versions were held: a 3-hour session specifically designed for the participant who offered 20 hours, and 1-hour sessions for other future participants.

For the 3-hour session, 72 loops were selected with a balance in genres of rhythm, each loop would be repeated for 3 times and the order of all 216 loops were randomised. For the 1-hour session, 24 loops were chosen from the 72 loops of the 3-hour session, also repeated 3 times and with the order randomised. In this set-up, it would be possible to obtain 3 versions of dualisations from each individual drummer, and a comparison between different drummers would also be possible. As mentioned above, the genre of the repetition experiment is adjusted, the distributions are plotted in figure 14 and 15.

Figure 14: Genre Distribution of the 3-hour Repetition Experiment

Figure 15: Genre Distribution of the 1-hour Repetition Experiments

Simple/Complex Data Collection

According to the comments and insights from the participant who did the 3-hour repetition session, a distinction was made between a simple dualisation that suggests only the skeleton of the original rhythm, and a complex version capturing more details. Therefore the remaining 273 loops were split into 4 sessions, and the participants could produce 2 versions of each session with a simple versus complex dualisations.

The complete distribution of the collected data can be seen in 3.2.

3.1.3 Experimental Set-up

As dualisation requires the distinction between notes played by the left and right hand, we were very lucky to be able to borrow a Roland HPD-15 drum pad [54] that distinguishes between left and right from the Phonos laboratory.

Figure 16: Roland HPD-15 drum pad that was used in the experiment to document left and right distinction, hence dualisation of rhythm. It was borrowed from the Phonos laboratory under the UPF.

In order to translate the preprocessed MIDI data into sounds, a VST instrument shall be used. For this experiment, the Neutral set in Fairfax vol.1 from Addictive Drums 2 [55] was used.

For the collection of data, Ableton [56] is being used to record dualisation from the drum pad. The data is structured in the following way:

1. 8 Crochets would be played to indicate tempo. The participants were instructed to play the last 4 crochets for synchronization purposes along the experiment.
2. 2 2-bar repetition of the loop. The last 2-bars will be recorded and repeated until the participant thought that they had done a satisfactory dualisation.

The delay compensation built within Ableton would be used to compensate for any delay, and it would be monitored during the experiment.

Figure 17: Set-up in Ableton. The first track labelled as “1 Addictive” would be playing the 2-bar loop from the Groove MIDI dataset, while the second track labelled as “2 MIDI” would be the recording of the dualisations. Red box: 4 crochets for synchronization purposes. Black box: recordings of the repeated loop. Blue circle: delay compensation.

3.2 Data Collection

Distribution of Data Collected

At the end 5 participants were recruited. 2 1-hour mass data collection experiments were done at the beginning, 1 3-hour repetition experiment and 4 1-hour experiments were done, and 5 2-hour simple/complex experiments were completed.

Mass Data Collection: 345 2-Bar Loops				
Set T1 - 72 Loops (Participant #1) Repetition 1 Session: ✓ Repetition 2 Session: x Repetition 3 Session: x	Set T2 - 72 Loops (Participant #2) Repetition 1 Session: ✓ Repetition 2 Session: x Repetition 3 Session: x	Set T3 - 72 Loops (No Attendees) Repetition 1 Session: x Repetition 2 Session: x Repetition 3 Session: x	Set T4 - 72 Loops (No Attendees) Repetition 1 Session: x Repetition 2 Session: x Repetition 3 Session: x	Set T5 - 57 Loops (No Attendees) Repetition 1 Session: x Repetition 2 Session: x Repetition 3 Session: x
Entire Set to Test: 345 2-Bar Loops				
Set 0 - 72 Loops (Participant #5) Repeated 3 times randomly without letting him know about repetitions <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: fit-content;"> 24 Samples from Set 0 (Participants #1, #2, #3, #4) Repeated 3 times randomly without letting him know about repetitions </div>	Set A - 69 Loops (Participants #4, #5) 2 repetitions: I. For simple dualization II. For complex dualizations	Set B - 68 Loops (Participant #5) 2 repetitions: I. For simple dualization II. For complex dualizations	Set C - 68 Loops (Participant #5) 2 repetitions: I. For simple dualization II. For complex dualizations	Set D - 68 Loops (Participant #5) 2 repetitions: I. For simple dualization II. For complex dualizations

Figure 18: The distribution of the data collected from all the experiments. On the top: original mass data collection plan; all 345 loops divided into 5 sets, each set with an increase in difficulty. Only 2 participants were recruited. On the bottom: Set 0 is the repetition experiment; 72 loops each repeated 3 times were presented to the participant. From the 2 loops in Set 0 24 were selected to do 1 hour sessions. Set A, B, C, D are the Simple/Complex data collection sessions. 5 sessions in total.

All the data collected were then cleaned and verified to ensure that they were correctly extracted.

3.3 Post-Experiment Questionnaire

This questionnaire consists of 3 parts: the first part is asking for some basic information, such as age and years of experience with the drum set; the second part is asking how meaningful the concept of dualisation is to the participants and how confident they are at achieving a successful dualisation that can trace back to the original polyphonic rhythm; and the third part is the relationship between dualisations and rhythm similarity metrics by [46], that is the importance of the four rhythmic descriptors in the three

frequency ranges when the participants were dualising the rhythms. The second and third part are quantised with numbers for the participants to choose from so that there will be a comparable value among the 5 participants.

The questionnaire is available in Catalan, Spanish, and English; the English version is attached below in Appendix 11.1.

After the questionnaire, an open interview was also conducted in order to inquire more details about the experiment. Participants were happy to share their opinions about the experiment itself, and some of their further ideas about the concept of dualisation.

3.4 Analysis Methodologies

With the various metrics of rhythm similarity introduced in section 2.3.2, the collected data will be analysed to answer our 3 research questions. The aim would be to answer the meaningfulness of the concept of dualisation to the musicians, the correlation within the same drummer, and the correlation between different drummers.

As both the MIDI dualisation and the questionnaires with open discussions were being collected, both quantitative and qualitative approaches are aimed at analysing the 3 research questions. Both of these methods will be elaborated in the following chapter of evaluation.

3.5 Availability of the Collected Data

The collected data, along with the answers of the questionnaires and jotted notes of the open interview can be reached in the github repository: https://github.com/behzadhaki/dualization_dataset.git

4. Evaluation

Our aim is to explore the concept of dualisation, subjectively speaking a highly intuitive and actual concept to myself, my supervisors, and almost all musicians I spoke to. With the data collected from the experiments, comparison can be made between the concept of dualisation and the actual performance from the drummers themselves. Therefore in the following paragraphs, the data as well as the interviews and questionnaires will be evaluated and compared, by first reviewing the various insights and ideas given by the participants before and after the experiments, and then computationally comparing the recordings. For the latter part, the representation methodology of the data will first be discussed, then the data will be compared according to individual participants and individual tracks, and at last a comparison between the dualisation form and different instruments will be drawn.

4.1 Meaningfulness of the concept of dualisation

The meaningfulness refers to both the worthiness and the doability of dualising rhythms. A qualitative approach will be applied here to evaluate the insights and ideas.

4.1.1 Open Interview

As the open interviews were conducted in a casual conversation manner without a set of questions, the content of these interviews can only be summarised; these will be discussed below.

Meaningfulness and Replicability

All of our participants were convinced that dualisation is meaningful; all of them mentioned that although this interpretation of rhythm is not frequently used thus might be a bit difficult at the beginning of the experiment, it is a very intuitive and understandable concept.

In the repetition experiments, often participants would notice the repetition of tracks without knowing beforehand. After being told there were repetitions and asked about their confidence in producing the same dualisations, they hold a strong belief that even dualisations would not be identical, they share a high similarity.

Universality of Dualisation

Moreover, they believed that there must be some degree of universality of dualisation among different drummers. One participant justified this idea by the snare drum tradition, which serves as a basis for all Western trained percussionists.

Thought Process, Extraction of Instrument and Effects on Genre

Another common discussion topic is the thought process behind dualisation. With the multiple recurrence of the same rhythm in the same experiment, they believed that an “evolution” of dualisation was in their mind: each time the rhythm appeared, they were able to listen more and rethink about the presentation of the essence using only left and right.

However, not all participants agreed on the interpretation of dualisation as a reduction of instrument numbers, that is the extraction of two main instruments that are able to represent the majority of the essence solely by the pair. Some believed that they had to first digest and comprehend the rhythm, then output it as a dualisation form.

One participant that agreed with the extraction model also stated that genre played a huge effect on which instrument to choose from; an example given by this participant is that for rock it might only be snare and kick because of the focus of strong beats, but for jazz influenced styles the hi-hat and the ride might be reached from the reduction as they emphasise on the lay back and swing.

4.1.2 Questionnaire Responses

The questionnaire can be separated into three parts as mentioned in Chapter 3.3. These three parts will be presented below, and evaluation will be done after.

Participant Background

Participant No.	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
Age	22	26	24	20	41
Years of Experience	9	10	10	11	25
Left or Right Handed	Right	Right	Right	Left	Left

Table 2: Part 1: Background of the 5 participants. Years of experience with the drum set.

As shown, all the participants have more than 9 years of experience with the drum set; although not all professional players, they can still be viewed as experienced percussionists. Participant #5 is a professional drum player that contributed to most of the recording.

Confidence on the Dualisations

In the following 2 parts, the range of possible answers is from 0 to 6. The questions of this part will be listed below:

- 1) How many rhythms in the experiment that you have successfully extracted the essence by 2 hands?
- 2) How intuitive do you think the rhythms are to let you have a dualised image in your brain?
- 3) How many dualisations that you played can be traced back to the exact original rhythm?
- 4) How many dualisations can be traced back to a similar version of the original rhythm?

	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	Average
(1)	4	3	4	3	6	4,0
(2)	5	2	6	5	4	4,4
(3)	1	3	3	3	6	3,2
(4)	2	4	5	4	6	4,2

Table 3: Part 2: Confidence on the Dualisations

Participant #5 has the highest confidence that there is a strong correlation between the dualisations and the rhythms. Others have doubt on whether it can be traced back to the exact original one, but most of them agree there is a universal comprehension on dualisation to some extent.

Relationship between Dualisations and Rhythm Similarity Metrics

The following part is a questionnaire on the importance of factors that affects the dualisation results from the participants, the left column will be the factor, and other elements will be the answer.

	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	Average
Number of Instruments	5	4	5	6	0	3,6
Division of Beats (8,16)	5	2	3	4	0	2,8
Tempo	2	2	3	4	0	2,2
Genre	6	5	5	3	6	5,0
Syncopation-ness	1	5	5	5	6	4,4
Dynamics	4	5	3	4	6	4,4
Density of Notes	4	5	5	4	6	4,8
Lo,Mid,Hi Distribution	5	4	2	3	6	4,0
LMH Syncopation-ness	1	4	4	2	6	3,4
LMH Dynamics	4	4	3	4	6	4,2
LMH Density	6	4	4	4	3	4,2
Familiarity of Rhythm	5	5	6	6	6	5,6

Table 4: Relationship between Dualisations and Rhythm Similarity Metrics. Lo, Mid, High is abbreviated as LMH, and the rows with LMH is related to the particular differences between low, mid, and high. Definition referenced from [46].

The genre of and participant's familiarity of the rhythm is the most important ones, while tempo, number of instruments, and division of beats matter the least. For participant #5, the differences between low, mid, high is very important, however to the other less experienced percussionists, it is less important as a factor to affect dualisation.

4.2 Dataset Analysis

As all of the participants believed that the concept of dualisation is meaningful and to some extent it is a universal concept among percussionists, it will be interesting to see if the data verifies various beliefs and suppositions.

4.2.1 Data Representation

HVO structure and Dualised Representation

The collected data has to be represented symbolically in order to be analysed. In the works by Magenta [8] a mathematical representation of MIDI has already been developed. In order to represent a 9-voiced drum set in a 32-beat MIDI (each MIDI loop consists of two bars, each bar with a semiquaver division) with a tensor, a 32 step tensor is used as a basis to describe all the events in each beat.

$$X = [x_0, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{30}, x_{31}]$$

Equation 5: A 32-step tensor X with each step describing a beat.

Each step is then represented by a 27-dimensional matrix, concatenated by 3 9-dimensional matrices. The 3 9-dimensional matrices describe accordingly the instrument hit, the velocity of the hit, and the offset.

$$x_i = [h_{i_0}, h_{i_1}, \dots, h_{i_8}, v_{i_0}, v_{i_1}, \dots, v_{i_8}, o_{i_0}, o_{i_1}, \dots, o_{i_8}]$$

Equation 6: Each matrix within a beat of the tensor X . h represents the hits, v represents the velocity, o represents the offset.

This HVO structure serves as a basis for the representation of dualisations. Since the data was recorded with a left and right difference, the original MIDI data has 2 voices in each dualisation instead of 9 of an entire drum set. As a preprocess, the 2-voiced dualisations were reduced to a single voice, while the hits are represented by numbers from 0 to 3: 0 for no hits from both hands, 1 for left only, 2 for right only, and 3 for hits from both hands. The velocity is flattened from the two voices to one.

$$x_i = [h_i, v_i, o_i] : 0 \leq h_i \leq 3$$

Equation 7: For the HVO for dualisations, each matrix within a beat of the tensor X . h is from 0 to 3, and v is flattened.

Metrics Normalisation

In order to compare different distances together, all the mathematical metrics of rhythm similarities were normalised to a distance with the range of 0 - 1, where 0 indicates low distance between two dualisations hence high similarity, and 1 indicates high distance hence low similarity.

The Cosine distance is defaulted to output a number in the range between 0 and 1, therefore normalisation is not needed.

As the Hamming and Levenshtein distance range from 0 to an integer that states the number of differences of two strings, they are normalised linearly with Equation 8.

$$\mathit{norm}_{\mathit{Ham/Lev}}(X) = \frac{x_i - \mathit{min}(X)}{\mathit{max}(X) - \mathit{min}(X)} = \frac{x_i}{\mathit{max}(X)}$$

Equation 8: Linear normalisation used for Hamming and Levenshtein distances. X represents all the possible distances within one method of comparison. $\mathit{min}(X)$ is set to 0 to retain the identical comparison of distance = 0.

The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient indicates the correlation between two lists by a number that ranges from -1 to 1, where 1 is positively correlated and -1 is negatively correlated. In the dualisation representation, both left and right should be interchangeable; therefore a negative correlation of left and right should be treated the same as a positive correlation, an absolute function is applied to the coefficient. As 1 indicates perfect correlation and 0 indicates no correlation, the complement of the absolute coefficient will be considered a distance with 0 indicating close relation and 1 indicating distant relation.

$$\mathit{norm}_{\mathit{Spearman}}(X) = 1 - |X|$$

Equation 9: Normalisation for the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

Similarly, the Jaccard Index outputs a number between 0 and 1 with 0 being no duplicates hence distant relation, and 1 being all duplicates hence close relation. Therefore the complement of the Jaccard Index will be considered the distance.

$$\text{norm}_{Jaccard}(X) = 1 - X$$

Equation 10: Normalisation for the Jaccard Index.

Note that these normalisations are merely a method to equate the different meanings of these metrics, so that the results from different metrics can be plotted onto the same graph and thus different behaviours can be compared for the metrics. It does not mean that the distances can be compared directly; the actual output of these metrics must be traced back to their working principles.

Weight Profile Choice

In the literature review section of 2.3.2, several metrics similarity and weight profile are introduced, especially the two metrical weight profiles that simulates the psychological accent given to individual beats.

In order to compare the two metrical weight profiles, the velocities are masked with three different situations: no metrical weight profile applied, the Lerdalh and Jackenoff profile [44], and the Palmer profile [45]. These three situations are applied onto the intra drummer distance as an example, which is defined as the distances between different dualisations of the same track by the same drummer. In order to compare results, a random term is added: it is the distance calculated between two randomly selected tracks. As these metrical weight profiles were masked onto the velocities, these three situations are all comparisons of the velocities of dualisations. In figure 19 the comparison can be seen; different distances were plotted for each participant, numbered from 1 to 5, and a random distance from two different tracks was added as a comparison. The difference between a random distance and an intra drummer distance is the largest while using the Lerdalh and Jackendoff profile, although it also suppresses velocities the most among the 3 situations, possibly overpenalising other factors such as syncopations that occur on the weak beat. Nonetheless, based on this result, the Lerdalh and Jackendoff profile was chosen for other analyses and applied on all velocities of the dualisations as it amplifies most the difference between the data and a random term, or in another aspect it is more suitable for a dualisation and it explains the results better.

Figure 19: A side-by-side comparison of the 3 profiles masked on dualiations of the same drummer. From top to bottom: No weight profile, Lerdahl and Jackendoff's [44], Palmer's [45].

4.2.2 Intra Drummer Correlation

Multiple participants mentioned in their open interviews that they had a strong belief that the different dualisations played by themselves would be extremely similar with variations, therefore the first analysis will be done on the intra drummer correlation, in other words how similar are the dualisations of the same track played by the same participant.

As in the repetition experiment every participant dualised the 24 tracks 3 times, intra drummer comparison is thus possible: for each participant, the 3 versions of dualisation from the 24 tracks are compared, and the distances between dualisations are recorded. All the metrics will be applied onto both hits and velocities except for the Jaccard Index; it is only applied onto the hits as there will be almost no identical term in the velocities, making the comparisons on velocities using the Jaccard Index trivial. The result distances are plotted in figure 20 and 21.

Figure 20: Intra drummer distances on Hits.

Figure 21: Intra drummer distances on Velocity.

The p-value also supports the above figures.

Participant	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	Random
p-value H	0,097	0,032	0,186	0,141	0,090	0,368
p-value V	0,051	0,007	0,055	0,011	0,009	0,269

Table 5: The p-value of a Spearman's correlation for each participant.

It is evident that the intra drummer distances are far lower than a random comparison from different tracks. This corresponds to and verifies the comments of the participants that they believed the 3 different versions would be similar, there is consistency of dualisation for a single musician.

4.2.3 Inter Drummer Correlation

Another claim from the participants states that dualisation is universal, that is the comparison between different drummers of the same track should also be correlated. This claim can also be verified through an analysis of distances between different participants per track.

Similar to the intra drummer, this inter drummer correlation can be found via the repetition experiments. Both hits and velocities are compared, and plotted below in figure 22 and 23.

Figure 22: Inter drummer distances on hits.

Figure 23: Inter drummer distances on velocities.

As shown, the difference between inter drummer distances and the random distances is not that obvious; the distances of velocity has better results than the hits, but there are still a lot of tracks equal or even more different than the random one.

As this result was unexpected, different comparisons have been done to see if there are any anomalies within the dataset. When the distances between different participants were compared and plotted together as shown in figure 24, the result of participant #2 attracted attention as the similarities between participant #2 and other participants are considerably low.

Figure 24: Heat map showing the cosine distance between all 5 participants. Shown diagonally, the distances of each participant compared with him/herself are much more correlated, hence high intra drummer correlation. Distances between participant #2 and others are high.

The anomaly of participant #2 can be further illustrated when heat maps of the dualisation of each participant are brought together. Figure 25 shows a set of heat maps of the merged dualisations of individual participants; the x-axis represents the time for 2 bars and the y-axis represents the velocity.

Figure 25: Heat map that merges all the dualisation of the participants. Numbers at the far left indicate which participant is. X-axis: time with 8 bars separated by grey columns, each subdivided into 4 semiquavers. Y-axis of each participant: Velocity, higher y equals a higher velocity.

Inter Drummer Correlation after Elimination of Participant #2

It is visible that the shape of the merged dualisations of participant #2 is vastly different from other participants; it suggests that participant #2 transforms notes heavily onto the strong beats when dualising the rhythms.

As suspicion arose about the validity of participant #2, the inter drummer correlation is re-ran without participant #2. The results are as follows, plotted in figure 26 and 27.

Figure 26: Inter drummer distances of hits without participant #2

Figure 27: Inter drummer distances of velocities without participant #2

The result has improved by ignoring the data from participant #2, especially the distances calculated on the velocities. Again, p-value shows this improvement although the improvement is not straightforwardly present in every track.

Figure 28: Plot of p-value of the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient with and without participant #2 using the hits as calculation of distances.

Figure 29: Plot of p-value of the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient with and without participant #2 using the velocities as calculation of distances.

As plotted above, the improvement of eliminating participant #2 does exist, but only to a limited degree. The more recognisable distances between dualisations of certain tracks are caused by participant #2 such as track 10 and track 15, but overall the inter drummer correlations are way less obvious than the intra drummer correlations.

4.2.4 Instrument Pair vs Dualisation Comparison

While not all participants agree, one of the comments from the participants is that dualisation is a reduction of instruments in a drum set, that is to represent a particular rhythm with only a chosen two to three instruments. Hence, an analysis on which instruments are represented by dualisation can reveal the relationship between instrument pairs with the dualisation, the essence of the rhythm can thus be traced back to the few condensed parts within the drum set if this hypothesis is true.

The methodology of comparing drum set parts to the dualisation is as follows: the 9 instruments within the drum set was reduced to 6 according to their functions, it is shown below in table 6; then every combination of 2 from the 6 instruments were singled out, and the distance between the 2 and the dualisation was calculated; finally data was recorded and a heat map of the mean distance for every element was plotted to see if specific instrument pairs stands out. The reason behind reducing instrument number is that with all the instruments, some combination is basically non-existent such as low tom and high tom played at the same time. The calculation of the matrix is shown below in equation 11, 12, and 13.

Original Instruments from GrooVAE	Reduced Instrument
Kick	Kick
Snare	Snare
Closed Hi-Hat	Hi-Hat
Open Hi-Hat	
Low Tom	Tom
Mid Tom	
High Tom	
Crash	Crash
Ride	Ride

Table 6: Reduction of instrument numbers for instrument-dualisation Comparison

$$\text{ConfusionMatrix} = \sum_{n=0}^{\text{len}(\text{Dua})} \frac{\text{PairComp}_{\text{Dua}_n, I_{i,j}}}{\text{len}(\text{Dua})}$$

Equation 11: Confusion matrix of comparing the distance between each pair of instruments and the dualisation. All possible dualisation combinations are taken the mean.

$$\text{PairComp}_{\text{Dua}, I_{i,j}} = \min(\text{dist}(\text{Dua}, I_{i,j}), \text{dist}(\text{Dua}, I_{j,i})) \mid i = [1, 6], j = \{x \mid x \geq i, x \leq 6\}$$

Equation 12: The distance calculation of every instrument compared with one single dualisation. PairComp is the matrix of pair comparison of instrument, Dua is a single dualisation, $I_{i,j}$ is the selected instrument pair; where i and j loops through all possibility without repetition by $i = [1, 6], j = \{x \mid x \geq i, x \leq 6\}$. The mean distance is taken with the instrument pair put into the distance calculation normally and reversely, compared with the dualisation.

$$\text{dist}(\text{Dua}, I_{i,j}) = (d_{\text{Lev}}(\text{Dua}_L, I_i) + d_{\text{Lev}}(\text{Dua}_R, I_j)) / 2$$

Equation 13: Distance calculation for this instrument pair and dualisation comparison. Dua is a 2-voiced dualisation, $I_{i,j}$ is the two selected instrument pairs. The distance is calculated as follows: the left dualisation part is compared to the first instruments, and the right dualisation part is compared to the right. The levenshtein distance is used for analysis. The mean value is then taken to represent the distance between the dualisation and these 2 instruments.

1. Combination of 2 instruments chosen

2. 2 sums of distances are calculated

Distance 1: mean of the 2 Levenshtein Distances

$$\frac{\text{Lev}(\begin{matrix} \text{Snare} \\ \text{Left} \end{matrix}) + \text{Lev}(\begin{matrix} \text{Kick} \\ \text{Right} \end{matrix})}{2}$$

Distance 2: mean of the 2 Levenshtein Distances

$$\frac{\text{Lev}(\begin{matrix} \text{Snare} \\ \text{Right} \end{matrix}) + \text{Lev}(\begin{matrix} \text{Kick} \\ \text{Left} \end{matrix})}{2}$$

3. Take the minimum of the 2 sums

Figure 30: Visualisation of one of the instrument pair calculation compared with one dualisation. For every dualisation, this process is repeated for every possible instrument pair without duplication, and all dualisations of each track are calculated.

The metric used here is the Levenshtein distance because it demonstrates the maximum difference. Other metrics also suggest similar results.

The mean of this distance of all tracks across all participants are plotted as a heat map in figure 31 below.

Mean Levenshtein Distance Comparison between Dualisation and Instrument Pairs of All Tracks

Figure 31: Heat map for the mean Levenshtein distance comparison between all dualisations and all possible instrument pairs of all tracks.

It is evident that kick, snare, and hi-hats captures more essence than tom, crash, or ride, but not very significantly. As one of our participants mentioned that the genre of the rhythm plays an important role on how the dualisation is being thought, the above process was repeated with every available genre. The scale of different genres are different, this is intentional as if all the distances were normalised into the same scale, genres with more notes (such as funk) will have a much higher distance than genres with less notes (such as pop). Hence, the scale is in accordance with the genre itself to enhance the instrument pair comparisons, and point out which drum pairs are able to capture the essence the best in a particular genre. Results are shown below in figure 32 and 33.

Figure 32: Heat map for the mean Levenshtein distance comparison between dualisations and all possible instrument pairs from individual genres. From top left clockwise: afrobeat, afro-cuban, dance, funk, hip-hop, jazz.

Figure 33: Heat map for the mean Levenshtein distance comparison between dualisations and all possible instrument pairs from individual genres. From top left clockwise: latin, pop, punk, reggae, rock, soul.

As shown above, participants extracted different instrument pairs from different genres, that is the essence of these genres exist the most in some distinctive instrument pairs. A few intuitive examples would be pop, punk, and rock rhythms were dualised using mainly kick and snare; jazz, latin, and reggae were focused mainly hi-hat and snare; and latin and afro-cuban rhythms carried a portion of tom toms.

This result thus confirms the claim that the dualisations of different genres have correlation with distinctive instrument pairs.

4.3 Summary of Evaluation

From the interviews and the insights of the participants, it is known that the concept of dualisation is meaningful to them subjectively.

It is also suggested that within every participant, different dualisations of the same track will be similar; this is evidenced by the sharp contrast between the intra drummer correlations and the random comparison.

Universality of this concept is also widely assumed, however, from the comparison between the inter drummer correlations and the random comparison, the universality of dualisation is not obvious. Even with the elimination of the data from participant #2, it still remains disputable.

Although not all participants thought that the essence can be portrayed only through 2 instruments, they all held a strong belief on the importance of genre as a factor of dualisation. With the comparison between dualisations and instrument pairs, the selection of any 2 instruments within a drum set can not portray all the genres and all the tracks perfectly, but by separating the analysis into different genre groups, the instrument pair choice becomes obvious.

5. Discussion

Contrasting with the previous attempt [10], a practical methodology with data collection and analysis is being used in this project. Based on the results of this varied approach, different ideas and understandings of the concept of dualisation have been expanded by experimenting and discussing with experienced percussionists. In this chapter, these new aspects will be first interpreted and discussed, and a few problems and limitations of this thesis will be elaborated, a conclusion will then be drawn and some of the possible future works after this collection of dataset will be briefly mentioned.

5.1 Interpretation of the Evaluations

There has always been a recurring theme during this entire project: the validity of dualisation. The beginning rationale was simply just to expand the dimension of rhythm representation from a single voiced tapping to a 2-voiced dualisation. However, too many factors were related to this concept despite the intuitiveness of dualisation. The aim is thus to verify the meaningfulness of this concept by examining the correlation between the dualisation and our perception of the essence of rhythm.

With this in mind, data collection sessions were conducted and a dataset of original rhythms and dualisations were prepared. This dataset served as the basis of the analysis. To adapt to the particular situation of not recruiting enough participants, different variations of the experiments have been adapted. One of the variations was the repetition experiment, in which every track was repeated three times in order to investigate the irregularities among different trials.

Analyses and evaluations have been carried out on the collected data to confirm the validity of dualisation. Although with minimum certainty, it could be concluded that there are evidences on the claims and assumptions from the participants, namely the meaningfulness, replicability, universality, and the effect of genres on dualisation.

5.2 Problems of the experimental set-up

From the open interviews, some participants mentioned that there were several problems of the experimental set-up that might affect the participants, and thus the dataset.

The rhythms were originally from the Groove MIDI dataset by the Magenta group[8]; the genres were unbalanced: the majority of the tracks are in the style of rock. This is a problem because of the data heavily biased towards the main styles, and neglecting styles with lower frequencies.

Figure 13: Distribution of the 345 loops used for the data collection sessions.

Another problem is the set-up. All the sessions were conducted in a room in the UPF campus, some frequencies of the drum were difficult to be identified and it affected the recordings. The sound of the drum VST also stays the same throughout the experiment, when in real life the timbre should reflect on the style. Furthermore, the sound device used is the Urban Box 7 produced by Energy Sistem [57], participants felt exhausted sometimes after long periods of time listening to this device.

Finally, because of the Groove MIDI dataset, all the tracks are heavily biased towards a Western influence; the snare drum tradition is thus enhanced, making the dualisation culturally based. Therefore, conclusions drawn using this dataset are not necessarily applicable onto other styles of music, and thus not reaching the human perception of rhythm itself.

5.3 Analysis Limitations

Due to time constraints and technical limitations, some of the proposed analytical tools were not applied. The metrics of rhythm similarity regarding the three frequency ranges were not thoroughly explored; they might have a huge impact on the interpretation of correlations as some participants rated them in high importance.

As this thesis focuses on the analysis of dualisations among different participants, parts of the dataset have not been used. More analyses can be done on how the participants slowly dualise a rhythm when the rhythm was on a loop in the recording sessions.

5.4 Conclusion

Our assumption on the concept of dualisation is its connection to our perception of “essence” of rhythms, and its universality that it is intuitive and trivially comprehensible to musicians. Considering all the problems in the experimental set-up and limitations on analyses, the correlation between dualisations and the assumptions can still be drawn to some extent. While the universality still remains disputable, there are still intra drummer consistencies, as well as the instrument pair and dualisation correlations according to different characteristics of genres and possibly other metrics.

As this dataset is just collected and due to time and technical limitations, the assumption can not be drawn with absolute certainty. However, this journey can be framed as a preliminary exploration of the collected data: correlations do exist between dualisations and our intuition, it is not an irrelevant concept that just exists in our brain but not the real world. It can be further interpreted as a way towards reaching the essence of rhythm, and as a symbolic representation it shows aspects that other representations might lack.

5.5 Future Work

One of the main possible future work is the elephant in the room: other analytical metrics. Not only the suggested ones in 5.3, there are a lot of other factors that might be related to dualisation, such as the effect of instruments, beat positions, metric role; these metrics can all be applied to both the original rhythm and the dualisations. By applying these analytical tools, the concept of dualisation can be further verified, and conclusions

can be drawn more specifically on the relation between this symbolic representation of rhythm and how we perceive rhythm.

Another possible future work is to develop a computational model to automatically dualise rhythmic patterns. With the data collected, the dataset can serve as a ground truth for the development of this model; and ideally this model would be able to resonate with the human perception of rhythm, and output dualisations that match our understanding.

By going beyond the monophonic symbolic representations of rhythm, more rhythmic analyses would also be able to be explored since less information is lost in a dualisation setting than a monophonic reduction. More complex and ambiguous relationships of rhythm might be available through the dualisation of rhythmic patterns.

These are however not the only possible future works to be done; I believe that by collecting and compiling this dataset, it can serve as a foundation for future research on this exact concept. By leaving the work at this point, I believe that continuations are easily accessible and I encourage future work on this intriguing topic.

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Toussaint, G. T. (2020). The geometry of musical rhythm: What makes a "good" rhythm good? Boca Raton, Florida: CRC Press, Taylor Francis Group. Ch. 32 p. 244

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Kung, S., Chen, J. L., Zatorre, R. J., & Penhune, V. B. (2013). Interacting cortical and basal Ganglia Networks Underlying finding and tapping to the musical beat. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, 25(3), 401-420. doi:10.1162/jocn_a_00325

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Kung, S., Chen, J. L., Zatorre, R. J., & Penhune, V. B. (2013). Interacting cortical and basal Ganglia Networks Underlying finding and tapping to the musical beat. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, 25(3), 401-420. doi:10.1162/jocn_a_00325

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Large, E.W., Herrera, J.A., & Velasco, M.J. (2015). Neural Networks for Beat Perception in Musical Rhythm. *Frontiers in Systems Neuroscience*, 9

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Image taken from

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Equation 4: Jaccard Index of 2 sets.

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10. Appendices

10.1. Appendix 1: Post-Experiment Questionnaire in English

Post-experiment Survey

General Information

What is your name and surname?

What is your age?

What is your main percussion instrument?

Any other instruments you play?

How many years of experience do you have playing your main percussion instrument?

Are you left handed or right handed?

left / right

Questions about the Experiment

How many rhythms in the experiment that you have successfully extracted the essence by 2 hands?

None 1 2 3 4 5 Everything

How intuitive do you think the rhythms are to let you have a dualised image in your brain?

Not intuitive at all 1 2 3 4 5 Very Intuitive

How many dualisations that you played can be traced back to the exact original rhythm?

None 1 2 3 4 5 Everything

How many dualisations can be traced back to a similar version of the original rhythm?

None 1 2 3 4 5 Everything

To what extent do you think the following factors affect your dualisation result?

Number of Instruments

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Division of beats (8-beat, 16-beat)

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Tempo

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Genre

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Syncopation-ness

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Dynamics

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Density of Notes

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Low (Kick, Low Tom), Mid (Snare, Side Stick), High (Hi-Hat, High Tom)

Distribution

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Difference of Syncopation-ness between Low, Mid, High

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Difference of Dynamic between Low, Mid, High

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Difference of Density of Notes between Low, Mid, High

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Your familiarity with the rhythm

Not important 1 2 3 4 5 Very important

Any other comments?